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Simulation and design of a small-sized pentagon broadband antenna for 5G connectivity

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Abstract: The development of fifth-generation (5G) mobile networks requires the creation of compact, efficient and broadband antennas capable of operating at high frequencies, including millimeter waves (25-40 GHz). Antennas for 5G should provide high bandwidth, low latency and high connection density. One approach to achieve these goals is to develop miniature antennas of unusual geometry, such as pentagon-shaped antennas. The pentagonal shape makes it possible to achieve efficient use of space and improve frequency characteristics, which makes it attractive for 5G devices. This article discusses the process of modeling a pentagonal antenna for 5G networks.

Keywords: pentagonal antenna, 5G, 25-40 GHz, 28 GHz, CST studio Suite.

Introduction

1. Antennas for 5G:

Features and requirements Antennas for 5G networks must meet the following basic requirements:

- **Broadband:** 5G requires an antenna capable of operating at frequencies from 24 to 40 GHz to ensure high bandwidth. **Compact:** 5G devices such as smartphones and IoT devices require miniature antennas that can be easily integrated into a limited space.

- **High efficiency and low losses:** it is necessary to minimize losses and ensure maximum gain.

- **Versatility:** Antennas for 5G often require radiation circuits with a wide coverage angle to ensure reliable communication in urban environments and

high device densities. A pentagonal antenna may be a suitable solution, as its geometry helps to achieve good agreement with transmission lines, broadband and compactness.

Another 902 / 5,000 5G antennas: specifications and requirements 5G antennas must meet the following key requirements:

- **Broadband:** To support high 5G bandwidth, antennas capable of operating at frequencies from 24 to 40 GHz are required.

- **Compact:** 5G devices such as smartphones and IoT devices require miniature antennas that can be easily integrated into a limited space.

- **High efficiency and low losses:** Antennas should minimize losses and provide maximum gain.

- **Omnidirectionality:** 5G antennas often require directional patterns with wide coverage angles to ensure reliable communication in urban environments and at high device densities. A pentagonal antenna may be a suitable solution, as its geometry helps to achieve good line alignment, wide bandwidth and compactness.

2. Design parameters of a pentagonal antenna.

When developing a pentagonal antenna for 5G, the following parameters must be taken into account:

- **Antenna shape:** The pentagon has a more complex structure compared to traditional rectangular or round antennas. This shape can improve the current distribution over the antenna surface, resulting in increased bandwidth.

- **Frequency range:** The antenna must be optimized to operate in the millimeter wave range, usually from 24 to 40 GHz. This requires precise selection of the length of the sides and corners of the pentagon.

- **Impedance matching:** For the antenna to work effectively, it is necessary to ensure matching with the typical transmission impedance (usually 50 ohms). This reduces reflections and improves power transmission.

- **Materials:** The materials used for the antenna must have high conductivity (for example, copper or aluminum), and also use low-loss dielectrics for the substrate.

3. The modeling process.

Electromagnetic modeling software packages such as CST Microwave Studio, HFSS, or MATLAB are used to simulate a pentagonal antenna for 5G. These tools allow you to perform three-dimensional modeling, analyze antenna characteristics such as radiation pattern, gain, standing wave ratio (VSWR), and calculate radiation losses and bandwidths.

Theoretical Framework for Antenna

Basic modeling steps:

1. **Setting the antenna geometry:** The first step is to set the exact dimensions of the pentagonal antenna. The length of the sides and the angles of the pentagon are determined taking into account the

resonant frequency of the antenna (for example, for a frequency of 28 GHz, the side length may be on the order of 2.7 mm).

2. Determination of substrate and materials:

The antenna substrate should be selected from a low-loss dielectric, such as Rogers RT/duroid, to minimize signal loss at high frequencies. Materials for the conductive parts of the antenna, such as copper or aluminum, are also specified.

3. **Frequency analysis:** The frequency analysis of the antenna in the range from 24 to 40 GHz is performed. This allows you to determine the main characteristics of the antenna, such as gain, impedance and bandwidth.

4. **Analysis of the standing wave coefficient (S11):** S11 is one of the key parameters indicating antenna alignment. The S11 value should be below -10 dB for all operating frequencies to ensure that the antenna emits most of the power supplied to it.

5. **Radiation pattern modeling:** A pentagonal antenna must provide multipath coverage, so it is important to analyze the radiation pattern to make sure that the antenna provides the required viewing angle and uniform energy distribution.

This paper focuses on the latter type of antenna, with the length of the grating side approximately $\lambda = \lambda_g$ as well as the small side's width $s = \lambda_g/2$, where λ_g is the controlled wavelength at the center operating frequency [3]. There are other parameters of the rectangular microstrip patch antenna: patch width (W), patch length (L), length and breadth (Wg) of the grounding plane, and substrate (grounding layer and middle layer) (Lg).

There are many ways to analyze an antenna made from a patch with a microstrip, including the transmission line representation and the recessed model. The most basic model would be the design based on transfer lines [4].

Fig. 1. Transfer lines marked pentagonal antenna signal generation source.

Transmission line equations [5].

To find the width (W):

$$W = \frac{c}{2 f_0 \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2}}}, \quad (1)$$

To determine the constant of dielectric impact:

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(1 + 12 \frac{h}{w}\right)^{-1/2}, \quad (2)$$

To determine the length that is most impactful or relevant:

$$L_{eff} = \frac{c}{2 f_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}}, \quad (3)$$

Fig 2. Illustrates the physical and effective lengths of a rectangular microstrip patch antenna.

To accurately ascertain the magnitude of the supplementary field effect within the lateral layer of the antenna:

$$(\Delta L):L = 0.412 h \frac{(\epsilon_{reff} + 0.3) \left(\frac{w}{h} + 0.264\right)}{(\epsilon_{reff} - 0.258) \left(\frac{w}{h} - 0.8\right)}, \quad (4)$$

To find the exact size L and the width and length of the ground connection (Ground):

$$L = L_{eff} - 2\Delta L, \quad (5)$$

$$L_g = 2 * L, \quad (6)$$

$$W_g = 2 * W, \quad (7)$$

For the design of microstrip feed lines using an inset feed configuration:

- Typically, the source of resistance is 50 Ω .
- Line width for microstrip feedings (W_f)

$$Z_c = \frac{60}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} \ln \left[\frac{8h}{W_0} + \frac{W_0}{4h} \right], \quad \frac{W_0}{h} \leq 1, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{120\pi}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}} \left[\frac{W_0}{h} + 1.393 + 0.667 \ln \left(\frac{W_0 + 1.444}{h} \right) \right]}, \quad \frac{W_0}{h} > 1, \quad (9)$$

Here, W_0 represents the width of the microstrip line, and Fi denotes the length of the inset.

$$fi = 10^{-4} (0.001699 * \epsilon_r^7 + 0.13761 * \epsilon_r^6 - 6.1783 * \epsilon_r^5 + 93.187 * \epsilon_r^4 - 682.69 * \epsilon_r^3), \quad (10)$$

The difference between patch and inset-fed is usually 1 mm.

We calculate W, L using Patch's equations:

$$W = \frac{c}{2 f_0 \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2}}}, \quad (11)$$

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(1 + 12 \frac{h}{w}\right)^{-1/2}, \quad (12)$$

$$L_{eff} = \frac{c}{2 f_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}}, \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta L = 0.412 h \frac{(\epsilon_{reff} + 0.3) \left(\frac{w}{h} + 0.264\right)}{(\epsilon_{reff} - 0.258) \left(\frac{w}{h} - 0.8\right)}, \quad (14)$$

$$L = L_{eff} - 2\Delta L; \quad (15)$$

$$L_g = 2 * L; \quad W_g = 2 * W, \quad (16)$$

$$fi = 10^{-4} (0.001699 * \epsilon_r^7 + 0.13761 * \epsilon_r^6 - 6.1783 * \epsilon_r^5 + 93.187 * \epsilon_r^4 - 682.69 * \epsilon_r^3), \quad (17)$$

$$f_0 = 2.4 \text{ GHz}$$

Rogers RO3203(lossy)

$\epsilon_r = 3.02$ $h = 0.2 \text{ mm}$ $t = 0.035 \text{ mm}$
 $W \approx 6 \text{ mm}$, $L \approx 10 \text{ mm}$, $Fi \approx 1.5 \text{ mm}$
We calculate the width W_f of the feed line:

$$Z_c = \frac{60}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} \ln \left[\frac{8h}{W_0} + \frac{W_0}{4h} \right], \quad \frac{W_0}{h} \leq 1, \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{120\pi}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}} \left[\frac{W_0}{h} + 1.393 + 0.667 \ln \left(\frac{W_0}{h} + 1.444 \right) \right]}, \quad \frac{W_0}{h} > 1, \quad (19)$$

Here, W_0 is the width of the microstrip line. (14)

Main Part

As you can see, the antenna elements have small dimensions because they are designed for the millimeter frequency range. Due to its low tangent losses, we employed Rogers 5880 as the substrate material for this study, chosen for its suitability in the high-frequency band. It was specially developed for the production of antennas for the fifth-generation millimeter networks of radio waves. Its parameters include a dielectric constant (ϵ) of 2.2 and a loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) of 0.0009. As for the supply point, it is usually located near the center of the antenna.

Workflow and simulation results in CST software. The result of intensive study and development efforts targeted at offering extremely accurate and effective computational solutions for electromagnetic design difficulties is the electromagnetic modeling program CST Studio Suite. It includes CST tools made specifically for the design and optimization of devices throughout a wide frequency range, from optical to static frequencies. In addition to electrical modeling, assessments of both mechanical and thermal effects are included in the studies provided. One of the best tools available for accurate and quick 3D simulations of high-frequency devices is CST Microwave Studio.

In CST studio suite, the following sequences are performed to design planar microscale grating antennas: The CST Microwave studio is chosen because the flat micro-scale grating antenna works in

the microwave frequency range. We will initiate a new project within the microwave section of CST Microwave Studio, where we will specify the wavelength of the antenna. In the CST Microwave studio, the ground and substrate of the flat micro-scale grating antenna are $W_g=11\text{mm}$; $L_g=31\text{mm}$; $H_g=0.38\text{mm}$; in the dimensions, we mark it as in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Ground and substrate of grating antenna.

The following images show the sequence of making one patch in CST Microwave studio. Patch sizes $L=6\text{mm}$; $W=10\text{mm}$; $H=0.2\text{mm}$; material Rogers RO 3203(lossy); $\epsilon=3.02$;

Due to the lack of instruments and equipment in the laboratory, it is not possible to measure the radiation pattern. Therefore, only results simulated in the CST software are presented. This article presents the E-field and H-field radiation patterns. Figure 8 illustrates the characterization of the radiation pattern for co-polarization in the E-plane, within a 28GHz broadband configuration. Radiation patterns are multidirectional. The gain is evenly distributed with a maximum amplitude of 31 dBV/m.

Fig. 6. Radiation pattern at 25GHz.

Fig.7. Radiation pattern at 28GHz.

Radiation diagrams were viewed at different frequencies (25-28GHz). These radiation patterns were significantly different from each other. In Figure 6, we can see the maximum radiation of the modeled antenna at 25GHz in flame color and its value is 6.995 dBi. The minimum radiated power is depicted in light green, equal to -7.485 dB. That is, we can call the light depicted in green color a side leaf, and the flame-colored light the main directed light.

In Figure 7, we can see that the 3D radiation at 28GHz is quite different from the radiation at 25GHz. One of these differences is that the primary beam is shifted to the right along the x-axis, and its radiated power is 7.122dBi. The minimum side radiation is -4.643 dB. So, it can be seen from these two pictures that the grating antenna we modeled has a better radiation level along the z axis at 25GHz.

Fig. 8. Parameter S of the modeled antenna.

Eigenfrequency of the modeled grating antenna Its value is 26.4 GHz, expressed in the frequency dependence graph of parameter S in Fig. 8. This frequency is the maximum radiated and received frequency for the modeled antenna.

Fig. 9. Depicts the radiation pattern of the modeled antenna in the horizontal plane at a frequency of 25GHz.

That simulated antenna's emission arrangement on the horizontal direction is shown in Figure 9. This diagram represents the propagation of a 25GHz beam at angles of 12 degrees and 105 degrees. The beam directed by the red line is the main beam and its value is equal to 6.39 dBi. The dispersion value of the side leaves is -11.1 dB.

Fig. 10. Illustrates the horizontal radiation pattern of the modeled antenna at a frequency of 28GHz

In Figure 10, we can see the radiation diagram of the modeled antenna in the horizontal plane. This diagram shows the 28GHz beam spreading at angles of 4 degrees and 69.9 degrees. The beam separated by the red line is the main beam and its value is 6.42 dBi. The dispersion value of the side leaves is -8.2 dB.

Simulation results and optimization

After modeling the pentagonal antenna, the results may include the following parameters:

- **Directional pattern:** It is important to check the directivity of the antenna and its coverage in the horizontal and vertical planes. The pentagonal shape

should ensure an even distribution of energy over a wide angle.

- **Gain factor:** It is necessary to achieve an optimal gain factor suitable for 5G tasks (usually about 5-7 dBi for millimeter waves).

- **Bandwidth:** The pentagonal antenna must provide sufficient bandwidth to support a wide range of 5G frequencies, which is critical for high data transfer rates.

- **S11 and VSWR:** These parameters help determine how well the antenna is aligned with the transmission line. Optimal values guarantee minimal power loss and high antenna efficiency. If the simulation results do not meet the requirements, optimization of the geometry, material, or other antenna parameters may be required. This may include changing the angles of the pentagon, its size, or the thickness of the substrate.

Conclusion

Modeling and designing a pentagon-shaped broadband miniature antenna for 5G networks is a promising direction in the field of antennas for high-frequency applications. The pentagonal shape allows you to achieve compactness and broadband, which is important for modern mobile devices and IoT solutions. Through simulation, key antenna parameters such as gain, bandwidth, and radiation pattern can be optimized, making these antennas suitable for integration into devices for 5G networks.

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